

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES FOR:

The correct name for an *Aquilegia* (Ranunculaceae) hybrid of the parentage *Aquilegia flavescens* × *A. formosa*

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Data table (as described in Groh et al. (2019) and Groh and Cronk (2020)).

collection number	Herb.	type	corolla width	spur length	blade length	blade width	anther exertion	sepal length	sepal width
3751	RM	paratype	1.61	1.52	0.41	0.55	0.85	1.72	0.64
3487	RM	paratype	1.69	1.79	0.55	0.63	0.88	2.07	0.72
3692	RM	paratype	1.88	1.37	0.74	0.5	0.79	1.66	0.58
3692	CM	paratype	1.91	1.45	0.67	0.61	0.65	1.83	0.7
3326	GH	type	1.92	1.83	0.56	0.6	1.01	1.89	0.62
3326	MO	isotype	1.92	1.82	0.69	0.63	0.87	2.2	0.68
3326	MO	isotype	2.07	1.5	0.56	0.78	1.02	1.98	0.79
3326	US	isotype	1.92	2.04	0.52	0.53	0.83	1.89	0.69
3326	RM	isotype	1.79	1.79	0.54	0.64	0.77	2.02	0.8
3326	CAS	isotype	2.02	1.87	0.53	0.74	0.95	1.96	0.85
3326	CM	isotype	1.54	1.84	0.46	0.54	0.9	1.88	0.56
3326	NYBG	isotype	1.73	1.81	0.46	0.58	0.81	2.15	0.57
3326	RBGE	isotype	1.885	1.715	0.51	0.675	0.965	2.125	0.625
MK_01	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.4	1.6	0.7	0.9	0.8	2.1	0.7
MK_02	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.3	1.5	0.6	0.9	0.6	2.3	0.7
MK_03	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2	1.4	0.6	0.8	0.9	2.1	0.8
MK_04	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.9	1.4	0.6	0.9	0.5	1.6	0.8
MK_05	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.1	1.2	0.8	0.8	0.7	2.1	0.6
MK_06	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.9	1.5	0.7	0.9	0.6	1.9	0.9
MK_07	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.1	1.6	0.5	0.9	0.6	1.7	0.8
MK_08	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.9	1.5	0.5	0.9	0.8	2.2	0.8
MK_09	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.3	1.5	0.7	0.8	0.6	1.8	0.8
MK_10	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.6	1.8	0.7	0.7	0.5	2	0.7
MK_11	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2	1.5	0.8	1	0.7	2	0.9
MK_12	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.2	1.2	0.6	0.8	0.6	1.9	0.8
MK_13	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.6	1.9	0.8	0.9	0.4	2.6	1.1
MK_14	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.8	1.2	0.6	0.5	0.7	1.7	0.7
MK_15	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2	1.4	0.6	0.8	0.6	2	0.7
MK_16	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2	1.5	0.8	0.8	0.5	2.1	0.8
MK_17	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2.3	1.2	0.7	0.9	0.9	2	0.7
MK_18	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.9	1.5	0.6	0.9	0.6	2.4	0.8
Mk_19	flav.	Mt. Kobau	2	1.6	0.6	0.9	0.5	1.8	0.8
MK_20	flav.	Mt. Kobau	1.8	1.4	0.6	0.7	0.6	2.1	0.8
RL_03	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.1	2.6	0.8
RL_06	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.1	0.3	0.3	1	2.9	1
RL_16	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2	0.2	0.3	1.5	2.5	0.7
RL_17	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.2	0.3	0.4	1.4	2.5	1
RL_19	form.	Rob. Lake	1.5	1.9	0.3	0.4	1.4	2.6	0.9
RI_20	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.2	0.1	0.4	1.4	2.3	0.9

RL_35	form.	Rob. Lake	1.8	2.4	0.2	0.4	1.6	2.7	0.8
RL_37	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.5	3.1	1
RL_47	form.	Rob. Lake	1.7	2	0.3	0.3	1.5	2.8	0.8
RL_61	form.	Rob. Lake	1.2	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.4	2.5	0.8
RL_62	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.3	2.5	0.8
RL_73	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.5	2.7	0.9
RL_77	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.3	0.1	0.4	1.5	2.7	0.9
RL_83	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2	0.2	0.3	1.5	2.6	0.9
RL_91	form.	Rob. Lake	1.4	2.2	0.2	0.3	1.3	2.6	0.7
RL_94	form.	Rob. Lake	1.9	2.2	0.3	0.4	1.6	2.7	0.9
RL_97	form.	Rob. Lake	1.7	2.4	0.3	0.4	1.1	3.1	1.1
RL_107	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.2	0.2	0.4	1.5	3	1
RL_115	form.	Rob. Lake	1.4	1.9	0.3	0.4	1.2	2.5	0.8
RL_117	form.	Rob. Lake	1.6	2.2	0.2	0.3	1.4	2.6	0.8

Suppl. Fig. 1. Linear discriminant scores in rank order (*A. flavescens*, yellow, *A. formosa*, red) and inverse rank order (type specimens, black triangles). The holotype is the blue triangle. Scores were calculated on *A. flavescens* vs *A. formosa* with type specimens undefined. Types were then given scores based on the species analysis. Analysis based on untransformed (raw) data.

Suppl. Table: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) Scores
LDA on raw data

Parental Scores:

A. flavescens LDA scores: (upper)average(lower)
(-4.0443) -6.0312 (-7.3611)

A. formosa LDA scores: (lower)average(upper)
(3.8729) 6.0312 (7.3717)

Types:

Number Herb.	Type	LDA score
3751 RM	paratype	-1.9128
3487 RM	paratype	-1.6663
3692 RM	paratype	-4.2024
3692 CM	paratype	-4.5946
3326 Harvard (GH)	holotype	-1.5934
3326 MO	isotype	-2.4344
3326 MO	isotype	-3.6754
3326 US	isotype	-0.74668
3326 RM	isotype	-2.1263
3326 CAS	isotype	-2.1715
3326 CM	isotype	-0.75799
3326 NYBG	isotype	-1.3846
3326 RBGE	isotype	-2.1444

Suppl. Fig. 2. Principle Components Analysis (PCA)

Suppl. Fig. 3. A plot of natural log (LN) ratios, using the four characters that have the highest positive and negative scores in the LDA: X/W: Stamen exertion (X)/corolla blade width (W) and S/L: Spur length (S)/corolla blade length (L). If X/W is greater than c. 1.1 but less than 2.7 (LN>0.1, <1) and S/L is greater than 2.7 but less than 6 (LN>1, <1.8) then the plant can be considered a hybrid (dashed rectangle in figure).

